

**EXPLORING THE EFFECTIVENESS AND LIMITATIONS OF
FLIPPED LEARNING IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: Flipped learning is one of the modern instructional models that reverses the traditional teaching process, and it becomes one of the most influential innovations in English language education. Instead of learning new material in class and practicing it at home, students first learn lessons through videos, readings, or other online materials beforeclass. Then classroom time is devoted to interactive, communicative, and problem-solving activities. This paper explores the effectiveness of flipped learning in teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL). Based on the works of Bergmann and Sams (2012), Bishop and Verleger (2013), Abeysekera and Dawson (2015), Zainuddin and Halili (2016), Thai et al (2017), and Ahmad et al (2020) it shows how this approach fosters learners' independence, engagement, motivation, and linguistic ability. The findings from existing literature illustrate that flipped learning increases students' participation which allows more individualized feedback, and creates more meaningful opportunities for language practice. However, limitations such as lack of digital technology in some learning facilities, especially schools, and not prepared students for the class, and lack of teachers' technological skills can be cause of challenges during class. The study integrates that flipped learning can improve EFL's effectiveness when supported by qualified teacher training and technological advancement.

Keywords: Flipped Learning, English as a Foreign Language (EFL), Learner Autonomy, Student Engagement, Motivation, Language Skills, Interactive Learning, Educational Technology

In today's modern world, technological advancement considerably transforms educational practices across the world. In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, for example, the traditional teacher-centered approach, where the teacher is a dominant of the learning process, is being criticized because of promoting passive learning and lack of communication. To solve this problem, professors found learner-centered teaching methods that improve independence, participation, and collaboration of students. One of the most effective teaching method is the flipped classroom or flipped learning, which reverses the learning process that includes learning new topic and materials out of the lesson (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In a flipped classroom, students watch lectures, videos, or read texts before participating class. This allows them to come with preparation for deeper discussion and practice during the class. This method gives a chance to teachers to be as facilitators instead of being information transmitters, focusing on thinking skills such as analysis, synthesis, and application. According to Bishop and Verleger (2013), the flipped classroom method contains active learning and students get knowledge through engagement and interaction. In the EFL settings, flipped learning provides more time for meaningful communication, which is important for developing skills, such as speaking, listening, and critical thinking. As Thai, De Wever, and Valcke (2017) studied, EFL learners can benefit considerably from this approach because it shows real-life use of English instead of memorizing grammar rules. That's why, understanding the effectiveness of flipped learning in EFL context is important for language learners and researchers who try to find the way of modernizing their teaching method.

Flipped learning as a pedagogical model has its own benefits in constructivism and Bloom's taxonomy. The main idea is that learners first learn topic independently and then use classroom interaction for higher cognitive processes. Bergmann and Sams (2012) were the pioneers of this model in secondary education. In their book *Flip Your Classroom: Reach Every Student in*

Every Class Every Day, they argue that pre-recorded lectures allow teachers to spend class time helping students who struggle the most. They emphasize that flipped learning gives teachers greater flexibility to personalize learning and provides students the chance to learn at their own pace. Abeysekera and Dawson (2015) examined flipped learning using motivational and psychological theories. They ascertained that the practice enhances intrinsic motivation, reduces cognitive load, and supports self-regulated learning. They went on to argue that effective flipped learning depends on well-structured material that balances autonomy and structure.

Bishop and Verleger (2013) published one of the earliest systematic reviews of the flipped classroom. They defined it as an "educational technique that consists of two parts: interactive group learning activities inside the classroom and direct computer-based individual instruction outside the classroom." Bishop and Verleger's study revealed that flipped learning encourages motivation and class participation but requires great student responsibility to prepare beforehand. In another large-scale study, Zainuddin and Halili (2016) explored flipped learning trends in different fields, such as language. Their conclusion revealed that flipped classrooms facilitate active learning, digital literacy, and peer-to-peer collaboration. Importantly, they found that EFL learners increased speaking confidence and in-class participation.

Thai, De Wever, and Valcke (2017) conducted a study on how flipped learning has an impact on university students and concluded there was remarkable improvement in performance, especially in speaking and listening. According to them, flipped teaching helps students internalize grammar and vocabulary more effectively since they get to use them within contexts. Finally, Ahmad, Yousuf, and Alam (2020) explained that while flipped learning has pedagogical advantages, its success is hinged on teacher collaboration and digital literacy. They stressed that the majority of teachers in developing countries are faced with constraints such as limited technological access and institutional support.

Consequently, these investigations indicate that flipped learning encourages learner interaction, cooperation, and communication—key facets of EFL success. But they also demonstrate that without pedagogical and technological support, the model cannot achieve its full potential. Finally, Ahmad, Yousuf, and Alam (2020) explained that while flipped learning has pedagogical advantages, its success is hinged on teacher collaboration and digital literacy. They said that the many teachers in developing countries have a problem such as limited technological access and institutional support. These researches show that flipped learning encourages learner interaction, cooperation, and communication. But they also indicate that without pedagogical and technological support, the method cannot achieve its full potential.

The article below is based on qualitative theoretical review rather than empirical data. The analysis focused on consolidating evidence from six key studies that relate to flipped learning and its application in EFL settings. The literature considered in the article was sourced from peer-reviewed journals and books from 2012 to 2020. All the studies were examined for significant themes such as learner motivation, participation, academic achievement, and teacher preparedness. A content analysis approach was used to identify typical arguments and theoretical frameworks. Quantification is not the intent of this paper, but to investigate theoretical explanations for why flipped learning is said to be effective. By exploring some of the different perspectives, the study provides a deep understanding of how flipped learning facilitates contemporary EFL teaching.

The literature considered presents excellent evidence that flipped instruction is a sound pedagogical method for EFL environments. Four consistent themes emerge in the analysis: learner motivation, learners' autonomy, academic success, and teacher readiness. Zainuddin and Halili (2016) confirmed that flipped classrooms are more engaging as they make students participate in active activities. Abeysekera and Dawson (2015) also believed that flipped models are more intrinsic as they give learners more control over the learning process. Under EFL

contexts, where motivation is usually a concern, the flipped model transforms learners from mere listeners to participators. These activities support learning and enjoyment of languages. One of the greatest advantages of the flipped classroom is that it allows students to learn at their own pace, Bergmann and Sams (2012) proposes. This is due to the fact that by learning at their own pace, students become responsible and self-disciplined, which are qualities that are crucial for a lifetime of learning. Abeysekera and Dawson (2015) supported this viewpoint since they posited that students develop metacognitive awareness through pre-class preparation. To EFL students, this autonomy becomes a higher level of assurance in the utilization of English outside the classroom.

Thai et al. (2017) also provided concrete empirical evidence proving that flipped classes enhance academic performance. They noted that learners who studied flipped EFL lessons achieved a greater score in listening comprehension and speaking skills tests than students who studied in traditional courses. Bishop and Verleger (2013) also noted that flipped instruction enhances understanding through active learning and immediate feedback. As such, not only do students retain more information but also employ it more effectively in communication. Although it has its advantages, several researchers highlight that the success of the flipped learning method mainly depends on teachers' digital knowledge and institutional support. Ahmad et al. (2020) warned that inadequately trained teachers might not be capable of developing effective pre-class content utilizing digital tools. In addition, students with bad internet connections may fall behind, and it leads to inequality. Consequently, if flipped learning is to be successful, schools and institutions need to invest in technological advancement and teacher training.

While there are benefits to the flipped classroom, there also are some drawbacks. Some students may be unable or unwilling to be self-disciplined and motivated enough to prepare for class beforehand. Other students can not be able to learn by themselves without the instruction of teachers. Abeysekera and Dawson

(2015) said that too much independence can lead to an increase of stress or confusion for low-achieving students. Moreover, in large EFL classes, it is difficult for teachers to control individual progress effectively. However, these arguments may be relieved by intelligent design. Pre-class material can be made students engage with by formative assessment, quizzes, and online forums. Mixed methods which combine online and offline study with frequent feedback can overcome most challenges.

Theoretical examination of existing research confirms that flipped learning is a robust and effective approach for teaching English as a foreign language. It facilitates learner-centered teaching by promoting interaction, collaboration, and critical thinking. If well applied, flipped learning will enhance autonomy, motivation, and academic achievement in EFL learners. However, the practice demands significant teacher training, student independence, and technology use to be sustainable. Flipped learning should not be considered a fleeting phenomenon but as an innovative pedagogy that transforms the teacher from a keeper of knowledge to one who facilitates. Future research should explore further on how flipped learning can be adapted for implementation in various cultural and institutional contexts, particularly in the Third World. With this model, teachers can better prepare learners to confront real-life communication and lifelong learning.

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